
NEP in the Perspective of Sustainable Development

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Introduction

Since the Independence, we have undergone various reforms in the education system. Because of the education reforms, we observed gradual changes in the mentality of our people. Previously majority of the whole population was denied education. Indian society had been divided into four Varnas and thousands of castes; every caste did its traditional work. The followers of Varnas and the caste system said that this system was given the God and no one has the right to change it. From Jyotiba Phule to Dr. B.R. Ambedkar there is a big struggle to get the right of education for all people. An education is a tool that can bring change in all walks of life. All developed countries pay too much attention to education than other things and provide a sufficient budget for it. In India education does not get due importance and it is always dominated by the upper caste community, hence we must be very careful about the education policy.

We are now implementing NEP in higher education, and it has been thought

that this move will lead to sustainable development. Before talking about NEP, we shall understand what sustainable development means. “Development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.” This definition is given in the Brundtland report in 1987. Sustainable requires a balance between socio-Economic and environmental considerations to ensure a livable and thriving world for all. Then we shall see what is the aim of NEP. It aims to transform the country into a vibrant knowledge society. Let us see whether NEP provides sufficient scope for the sustainable development of students in the acquisition of language skills.

Objective:

The objective of this research paper is to study the ground reality of Indian society from the perspective of sustainable development and observe the NEP as a role model.

Method:

The analytical method will be used in the present research paper.

Sustainable Development:

Sustainable development means the comprehensive development of anyone who is involved in it. We shall see some key features of the sustainable development such as: Economic sustainability, Social and Environmental sustainability, etc.

Economic Sustainability:

We should have economic growth and prosperity but must minimize waste and pollution. If we do not minimize waste and pollution our all efforts will meet no end.

Social Sustainability:

It ensures that all people of the country have access to basic needs like food, water, education, health and education.

Environmental Sustainability:

The environment is the backbone of all living beings, and if it is polluted, we will destroy this earth and ourselves. We must keep the environment in its natural tune.

NEP:

The New Education Policy introduces a revised school structure, multidisciplinary education, language policy, assessment reforms, skill courses, and other changes. Policymakers have advocated for its advantages and challenges, too. Now we shall study it minutely in light of reality and aware common people. We try to find out

answers to a few questions that are very important and these answers will justify it in a real sense. These questions are: Does this policy follow the law of the constitution? Is it suitable for our education system? Will it be applicable in a large classroom? What is the place of student and teacher in it? Does it impose a dominating class ideology on a majority of people?

The constitution of our country ensures free, compulsory, and quality education for all children irrespective to their caste, race, clan, religion, etc. Govt of India passed the Right to Education Act in 2010 which also ensures the same thing given in the constitution. According to NEP low enrolment schools and colleges will be merged into big schools and colleges, all schools and colleges will be autonomous after five years and they will be free to charge fees from students as they like, they also appoint teachers on a contract basis, etc. The constitution adopted a reservation policy to provide adequate representation to all communities in all institutions. In NEP, education is a business and students is a customer. Then how we observe adequate representation in it.

These rules are just shocking and against the spirit of the Constitution. Will autonomous schools and colleges provide education to poor students? Will a teacher feel safe on a contract job and do justice to students? Answers to all questions are negative. After all who will monitor all

autonomous schools and colleges, only high caste and capitalists will run it. Then what happens to downtrodden people? Most of the downtrodden students will leave schools and work on daily wages to run their livelihood.

The model of NEP is taken from a developed country and directly introduced without thinking over the mentality of our students. Indian students are not mature enough to accept such a policy. Our classrooms are large, our attendance ratio is low and there is a great lack of infrastructure, Majority of people are not economically capable to offer higher education without the support from Gov., etc. In such conditions, we are not spoiling this generation. NEP can throw them out of the mainstream of education.

Language acquisition skills are important in this age of the communication revolution. NEP introduces the mother tongue in primary education but in higher education it is not compulsory. Students are free to choose any one language. A teacher will be provided after sufficient enrolment to a subject. It means there will be no qualified teacher then how can students learn a second language? English is a window to look at the world and is a language of communication and commerce, so why do we remove it from the compulsory basket of subjects? Do we have language lab and experts as per student ratio? No, it is the answer. A child acquires the skills of mother's tongue from family members. A child does not have any

problem talking while communicating in his language. His brain is set up to generate the language he uses, but the challenge is to speak in a second language. Instead of focusing on English, Hindi and Sanskrit language given the upper hand. How can we compete with the world by having such attitudes towards education and language.

NEP has introduced a new subject that is found in the syllabus of every class from bottom to top. Indian Knowledge Tradition, this subject is compulsory for all students. No doubt that our children should learn the knowledge tradition of our country. But only Hindu philosophy and literature are prescribed in the syllabus. Is there no knowledge tradition in Buddhism, Islam, Shikh, Christianity, Jain, etc? Is this policy going to impose the Vaidik philosophy? Scholars and educated people are doubtful on introducing one religion in the syllabus.

Conclusion:

Now there is a need to review the New Education Policy and make it suitable to our socio-economic condition. The policymakers must ensure that will follow the principles of the Constitution while framing any policy. Education must be free, compulsory, and qualitative. No one should miss education because of money, caste, class, religion, language, etc. If we provide quality education in return we will get quality basic generation that can make our country developed in the world.

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